

White Paper

**Task Force 4: Cross-cutting issues: Business
& Finance, data, education & upskilling**

Topic C: Education and upskilling

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Executive summary

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating issues related to smart buildings: their objective is to identify the remaining challenges and barriers to smart building deployment, and the associated research and innovation gaps that should be addressed in the near future.

*Task force 4 on Cross-cutting issues addresses the transversal requirements (business & finance, data, education & upskilling) to support the market uptake of smart buildings, and the strengthening of the related ecosystem. The third topic addressed by this task force and presented in this paper is **Education & Upskilling**.*

To reach the EU targets, the building sector must deliver a smarter, more flexible and resilient data-driven built environment. The built environment is increasingly embracing digital technologies, including control and automation systems, and as such is paving the way to smarter ways of managing our buildings and wider infrastructures. Digitalisation implies major changes in design methods, technologies and tools. Beyond BIM, in the light of technology advancements and societal changes related to buildings in the Industry 5.0 era, there will be a fundamental shift in designing and constructing smart buildings. With about 95% of its construction chain composed of SMEs and micro-enterprises (ECTP, 2019) characterised by low rates of technological adoption and innovation activity, and decreasing efficiency, digitalisation of SMEs in the construction sector is strategic for the EU. As pointed out by the European Commission¹, “the transformation towards a climate-neutral building stock will only be possible if existing jobs are transformed to include green and circular skills and if new job profiles emerge, such as specialists in deep building renovation, installers for advanced technological solutions, or Building Information Modelling managers”. However, construction sector workers are typically not knowledgeable or lack access to digital tools that could facilitate their work: providing lifelong (digital) skills development for (blue-collars) employees within the construction sector through trainings is a priority.

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- How can the evolution of businesses (digitalisation) be better supported through training?
- How to promote and implement the upskilling of the construction sector workforce for skills related to smart buildings (e.g., energy efficient and smart solutions, user-centric dimensions), together with continuous improvement?
- What are the needed tools to enable mutual recognition of skills and qualifications?

In its first part, this paper provides a state of the art regarding the following issues, specific attention being paid to EC-funded projects:

- Better integration of skills related to smart buildings in curricula (vocational education / blue collars as well as academics and white collars)
- Upskilling and continuous training of the construction sector workforce
- Mutual recognition of skills and qualifications: certification, training passports
- Support to the digitalisation of businesses (one-stop shop platforms, whole value chain approach, revised procurement processes)

A brainstorming process with the task force members then enabled to identify some key barriers and drivers regarding the digital education and upskilling of the construction sector workforce. The next diagrams provide an overview of the main barriers and drivers discussed.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/eu_renovation_wave_strategy.pdf

BARRIERS	
VALUE CHAIN	Fragmented and competitive sector, with a lot of SMEs, leading to complex communication, coordination and cooperation among trades
	Insufficient up-to-date knowledge of smart technologies (and 'soft skills' to sell them) and lack of companies able to provide training about latest products
	Lack of construction workers, ageing workforce
SOCIAL	Smart buildings still perceived as a niche market, hence limited resources and long-term investment by contractors, starting with training (time, money)
	Resistance to change, lack of awareness of the value of energy skills, lack of motivation to get trained on smart buildings topics
TECHNICAL	Vendor lock-in with proprietary software, lack of interoperability and lack of open standards/communication protocols
	Outdated curricula, not able to keep up with the rate of innovation, lack of competent trainers, limited training infrastructure
	Complex training landscape
ECONOMIC	Cost of upskilling trainings and uncertainty on available incentives and funding
	Lack of financial resources for training centers to update programmes and their teaching material
REGULATION	Lack of a regulatory enforced smart building standard, which complicates the market and hinders the development of effective and up-to-date vocational education programmes

Top barriers according to the Task Force

Figure 1: Overview of main barriers

DRIVERS	
VALUE CHAIN	Construction sector becoming more and more digitalised and technology-driven (BIM, automated off-site construction, etc.), creating a high demand for digital skills
	Market driver: Increasing demand for smart building, driving the demand for skilled workers
	Successful examples of clustering between like-minded companies (including cross-training and exchange of good practices)
SOCIAL	Digital skills are improving and spreading with digital natives and Covid-related digitisation
	Growing interest of workers to have a purposeful job and getting trained for that (with a strengthening image of apprenticeships in Europe)
TECHNICAL	Availability of new tools to involve all stakeholders of the value chain (e.g. BIM with freeware viewers)
	Push to create synergies and collaborations among Vocational and Education Training centers and High Education Institutions that will develop common educational curricula
ECONOMIC	National financial / tax incentives and other funding opportunities for training
	Availability of EU funds, for instance Erasmus+
REGULATION	Cost-effectiveness of upskilling in comparison to costs associated with lay-offs, unemployment and recruitment
	New EU legislations, to be transposed in the Member States, adding new requirements for smart building (e.g. in EPBD), and taking into consideration training and certification
	EPBD's SRI future implementation leading to a standardisation of smart buildings and growth of smart buildings-related training

Top driver according to the Task Force

Figure 2: Overview of main drivers

Based on the State of the Art and the barriers and drivers, a number of research and innovation gaps were identified. They are synthetised in Figure 3 and Figure 4 with the ones in bold being those that were identified as priorities in the last meeting with the task force members).

The identified ‘gaps’ will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

Figure 3: R&I gaps

Figure 4: ‘Go-to-market’ gaps

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List of abbreviations

aaS	As a Service
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BM	Business Model
BMS	Building Management Systems
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand Side Management
EC	European Commission
EHEA	European Higher Education Area
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Contracts
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
ESCO	Energy Service Company
eVs	Electric Vehicles
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEQ	Indoor Environment Quality
IFC	International Foundation Class
IoT	Internet of Things
KET	Key Enabling Technology
LLL	Lifelong learning
NQF	National Qualifications Framework
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TF	Task Force
VET	Vocational Education and Training

1. Introduction

This white paper is produced in the context of the SmartBuilt4EU project, a coordination and support action funded by the European Commission to bring together the research and innovation community on smart buildings.

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces with volunteers all across Europe, investigating topics related to smart buildings. They respectively address the interaction between building and end-user, efficient building operation, interactions between the building and the external environment, and cross cutting issues.

Figure 5: The four task forces set up by the SmartBuilt4EU project

SmartBuilt4EU task force 4 on cross-cutting issues addresses the transversal requirements (business & finance, data, education & upskilling) to support the market uptake of smart buildings, and the strengthening of the related ecosystem.

The Task Force focuses on 3 topics (one per semester):

- **Topic A: Smart financing & business models:** New services and business models (incl. building as a service), integration of new enabling technologies for innovative business models (e.g. blockchain)
- **Topic B: Data governance, privacy and security:** Data ownership and accessibility, regulations protecting the consumer, cyber-security, data privacy & protection
- **Topic C: Education and upskilling:** Better integration of topics related to smart buildings (e.g. smart solutions & user-centric dimensions) in curricula of academic and vocational education, upskilling and training of the building value chain, support to the evolution of businesses (getting digital)

The present white paper focusses on the third topic, i.e. ‘**Education & upskilling**’. It presents the outcomes of a collective work, carried out with the members of the task force, in several steps:

- Agreement on the scope
- Review of the State of the Art and identification of the points to be investigated in particular
- Analysis of barriers and drivers
- Identification of R&I gaps

2. Topic under investigation by the Task Force

2.1. Rationale

To reach the EU targets, the building sector must deliver a smarter, more flexible and resilient data-driven built environment. The built environment is increasingly embracing digital technologies, including control and automation systems, and as such is paving the way to smarter ways of managing our buildings and wider infrastructures. The digitalisation of our economy and industrial sectors is affecting the demand for learning and education (Sony and Mekoth, 2022; Palazzeschi et al., 2018). Industrial processes are constantly changing, prompting the need for employees to engage in active learning, training, and education (Bode et al., 2018; Störmer et al., 2014). As an example, the recent adoption of building information modelling (BIM), and the quest to decarbonise our built environment, have impacted several segments of the supply chain, including design, and engineering practitioners, prompting the need to redefine the construction personnel roles along with associated skills and competencies (Hodorog et al., 2020). Beyond BIM, in the light of technology advancements and societal changes related to buildings in the Industry 5.0 era, there will be a fundamental shift in designing and constructing smart buildings. With around 95% (ECTP, 2019) of its construction chain composed of SMEs and micro-enterprises characterised by decreasing innovation activity, low rates of technological adoption and decreasing efficiency, digitalisation of SMEs in the construction sector is therefore strategic for the EU. However, construction sector workers are typically not knowledgeable or lack access to digital tools that could facilitate their work: providing lifelong (digital) skills development for (blue-collars) employees within the construction sector through trainings is a priority.

This white paper therefore aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- How can the evolution of businesses (digitalisation) be better supported through training?
- How to better integrate skills related to smart buildings (e.g. energy efficient and smart solutions, user-centric dimensions) in curricula of academic and vocational education?
- How to promote and implement the upskilling and continuous training of the construction sector workforce, together with continuous improvement?
- What are the needed tools to enable mutual recognition of skills and qualifications?

2.2. Scope

The purpose of this section is to define the scope of the topic being investigated. Potential interactions with other topics addressed by the different SmartBuilt4EU Task Forces are also clarified.

The following ‘blocks of knowledge’ were identified by the Task Force:

- **Better integration of skills related to smart buildings in curricula**
 - vocational education / blue collars as well as academics and white collars
- **Upskilling and continuous training of the construction sector workforce**
 - Living labs, digital modules, real-life case studies, mentorship
- **Mutual recognition of skills and qualifications**
 - Certification, training passports
- **Support to the digitalisation of businesses**
 - One-stop shop platforms, whole value chain approach, revised procurement processes

3. State of the Art

3.1. Literature review

3.1.1. Education and training landscape

In many countries in the world, young people have to make an important decision at the end or at a certain stage of their compulsory education, between either general education or vocational and technical education (Berk, 2022). General education aims to improve skills that are generally useful in all professions (e.g., literacy, numeracy) but does not aim to prepare individuals for a particular profession or group of professions. Meanwhile, vocational and technical education aims to develop skills for a specific group of professions, a specific profession, or a specific type of business (Cedefop, 2017).

As part of general education, **higher education** is tertiary education leading to award of an academic degree. Each EU country has its own individual higher education system – but all are part of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). The EHEA system helps ensure that higher education systems across Europe are compatible - and that students, researchers and academics in Europe can collaborate and study or work abroad more easily². Qualifications across Europe are comparable through the [European Qualifications Framework](#) (EQF).

Initial and continuing vocational education and training are quite separate: initial VET (IVET) is usually part of a highly regulated school system, while continuing VET (CVET) is more heterogeneous.

Cedefop defines CVET as “education or training after initial education and training – or after entry into working life aimed at helping individuals to improve or update their knowledge and/or skills; acquire new skills for a career move or retraining; continue their personal or professional development’”. According to Cedefop (2019), there are many dominant conceptions of CVET in European countries. CVET often refers to education and training that is carried out after initial regular formal education, and is understood as:

- job-related/occupation-specific non-formal education and training for adults;
- job-related/occupation-specific formal education and training for adults;
- as part of further education and training or lifelong learning for adults.

² <https://education.ec.europa.eu/study-in-europe/planning-your-studies/higher-education-in-europe>

CVET is a main pillar of adult **lifelong learning** (LLL), lifelong learning referring to all learning activity undertaken throughout life, which results in improving knowledge, know-how, skills, competences and/or qualifications for personal, social and/or professional reasons (Cedefop, 2019).

3.1.2. Integration of skills related to smart buildings in initial education

Recent years have seen unprecedented growth in wireless and mobile devices, low-cost sensors, ubiquitous connectivity, and network communication speeds, with the boom in web-connected devices anticipated to have a global market impact of \$11.1 trillion per annum by 2025 (Manyika J, Chui M, Bisson P et al., 2015). As well as improving acceptance of pervasive technology, this has caused a shift towards cyber and physical system integration (Miorandi D, Sicari S, De Pellegrini F and Chlamtac, 2012) which is often referred to as IoT (Internet of Things). While such connectivity is not a new concept, its scale has accelerated recently due to reduced costs associated with hardware, improving communication networks, and strong economic, social and political drivers for change (Gubbi J, Buyya R, Marusic S and Palaniswami M., 2013). This changing landscape is rich with opportunities for built environment assets, yet this is hampered by legacy data formats, business processes, and **skill shortages** (Howell and Rezgui, 2018). **Construction companies, in particular SMEs, are indeed struggling to keeping up with the pace of innovation (in terms of skills and investment).**

In this context, the value chains involved in the design, construction, operation, and dismantling/recycling of smart buildings should acquire the skills that address the following challenges (Rezgui and Miles, 2011):

- How to conciliate, interpret and make sense of the diverse, rich, and dynamic data from various sources related to a building, the external environment (climate, surrounding natural and built environment), and internal occupancy and related processes?
- How to inform stakeholders' decision making during the design, construction, maintenance and operation of smart buildings leveraging on dynamic data, by drawing on complex systems theory, material sciences, human behaviour and other related areas?
- How to confer buildings a level of autonomy, awareness and resilience in the wider district and city scale?

The overarching aim is to train the current and next generation work force to exploit the fundamentals of complex systems applied to smart buildings to deliver new or refurbished built assets that (a) address lifetime requirements and (b) can perform optimally within the constraints of unknown future scenarios (Rezgui and Miles, 2011; Howell and Rezgui, 2018). This requires (a) a clear understanding of skill shortages to address this smart transition of buildings, (b) a holistic and integrated approach to delivering training.

In this context, blue and white collars in the construction industry are increasingly feeling the pressure to continuously train, educate and retrain (Wulfken & Müller, 2017) to remain competitive and increase their adaptability potential to the job market in this evolving smart building landscape (Sony & Mekoth, 2022). Consequently, employees will have to continuously unlearn, learn, train, and educate themselves in several areas related to their core expertise (Schallock et al., 2018), in an autonomous and self-organised manner (Adam et al., 2019).

It is interesting to note that as the imparted training changes, the workforce will begin to divide into an older cohort which received 'traditional' training and a younger cohort which received 'future-thinking' training. This dichotomy presents both intergenerational training opportunities and management challenges in organising a workforce with a non-uniform core skill set (Bergsagel and Isaac, 2022). As such, **integration and promoting increased demand for skills to design, construct, operate, and recycle smart buildings will be a priority for the years to come.**

To address this new demand for skills, a few new curricula related to smart building are already emerging (e.g. through Polytech Orléans and Polytech Nice Sophia Antipolis in France, both being accessible to students from higher and vocational education) and should provide good practices in the years to come on how to better integrate skills related to smart buildings in initial education.

The integration of ICT skills in initial education will also enable the construction sector to attract new types of profiles, and make the sector more attractive, thereby helping to tackle the issue of construction workers shortage thanks to an inflow of young workers. Construction indeed ranks third in the list of shortage occupations (ELA, 2021).

Smart technology can help solve the skills shortage in the construction industry in two ways: first, by helping today's construction workers do their jobs better, faster and safer; and second by helping attract new workers to jobs in construction³. **A paradigm shift from a business model focused on cheaper and precarious labour to a model promoting training, good working conditions and career opportunities (including for women) is urgently required and will only be achieved through a collaborative effort from both industry and education.** According to ELA (2021), EU and national campaigns could promote the usefulness of acquiring medium level vocational qualifications – particularly vocational qualifications associated with construction and engineering.

3.1.3. Upskilling and long-life training of the construction sector workforce

More training, reskilling (i.e. teaching the skills for an entirely new occupation) and upskilling (i.e. teaching advanced skills for their current occupation) of workers is needed, particularly because the renovation wave and Green Deal require a new, smarter way of building with new materials and technology.

It is difficult to quantify exactly how much reskilling is needed across Europe, according to the European Federation of Building and Woodworkers⁴, but they estimated end of 2021 that every year 5% of Europe's workforce will need to be retrained– meaning a quarter of the workforce needs to be retrained over the next five years.

With regard to the upskilling of construction workers, continued skills development through training to stay on top of the latest technologies is critical.

Training remains an important issue that is under-addressed in the construction sector, and when available it is organised on a vocational and/or voluntary basis (i.e. undertaken for reasons of continuing personal development). Individuals in the workforce need to continue to learn, update and add to their skills in order to remain employable, have the right skills to address current industry challenges, and thus add to the competitiveness of the construction sector.

The construction sector faces many problems with people development because of continuous change in working practices, new technological developments, lack of training and learning, and poor people management (Vakola and Wilson, 2004). **Lifelong learning is considered as a critical success factor in order to support cultural changes and has the potential to attract and retain young and qualified people to the industry.**

There is growing recognition in the construction sector that the potential benefits of technical and process innovation can only be realised through individuals at all levels learning and developing a considerable array of new capabilities. The required capabilities will not, in the main, be developed through traditional training courses but through the creation of well-planned learning opportunities in a supportive learning environment.

The imperative to transform organisational culture and working practices has profound implications for individual and organisational learning. For example, while partnering arrangements offer significant benefits to all stakeholders, these will only be realised fully if individuals such as the supervisors, construction

³ <https://www.international-construction.com/news/how-to-solve-construction-s-skills-shortage/8018296.article>

⁴ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/energy-environment/news/eu-confronted-with-lack-of-skilled-labour-to-support-building-renovation-wave/>

engineers and site workers understand the concept and the implications of the new arrangements induced by the smart building transition: thus individuals accustomed for most of their employment history to simply following instructions must migrate from a largely passive role to an active role where they take responsibility (planning, anticipating requirements, troubleshooting, communicating, monitoring and reporting etc). This represents an enormous challenge and will require an integrated change strategy for learning and training at corporate and at sectoral level (Rezgui, Y. and Miles, J, 2010).

Establishing **vertical and horizontal skills alliances within and across different disciplines in construction industry education and training** could foster increased collaboration and innovation for the future (Vakola and Wilson, 2004).

As discussed earlier, construction partnerships are less natural learning entities than are single organisations (Larsson et al., 1998). The reasons should be understood and addressed before planning training and learning are addressed. Hence, a particular attention should be given to the dynamics of these project-based alliances.

Organisations need to analyse and map available skills within across their departments and subsidiaries. An approach making use of a combination of a process and user-driven analysis can be adopted. The process-driven analysis will build and extend the work involved in understanding and mapping corporate business processes and attempt for each process component (including activity/task) identify company staff that enable, control, and perform the activity/task. The user driven analysis will establish a profile of each employee and highlight current qualifications, roles, responsibilities, core competencies, areas of expertise, past and ongoing achievements and experiences (e.g. projects), etc.

Roles have responsibilities attached to them and can be discharged by one or several persons. It is important to understand the skills that are required to perform a role and ensure that individuals who are in charge receive the right training to perform their duties. In that respect, roles need reviewing and creating to ensure that learning and training strategies get adopted and implemented (Rezgui and Miles, 2010).

This will provide a general picture about the capabilities and ICT literacy of the company staff, which can give interesting indications about the level of maturity of the business processes described earlier. There are obvious **skill gaps in the sector due to a weak ICT literacy from employees and lack of education and training support within most organisations**. Training courses to deliver the above skills tend to be vocational and/or voluntary (i.e., undertaken for reasons of continuing personal development). It is argued that a more strategic approach should be taken.

Individuals need the skills to embrace a knowledge culture, use technology and adopt and adapt to new working practices. There is a need to encourage employees 'to work smarter not harder'. This can be achieved in most organisations through identifying people who are interested in finding better ways of doing things and giving them opportunities to explore options and to introduce new methods and systems on a carefully monitored trial basis, as a preliminary to wider roll-out.

Innovative approaches to encourage SMEs to train their employees despite their reluctance have already been successfully tested. They include for instance on-site training and mobile training centres (see Figure 6), which could be tailored to the needs of smart buildings.

Figure 6: Mobile training centre by Practee Formation

3.1.4. Mutual recognition of skills and qualifications

The first principle of the EC European Pillar of Social Rights (Hodorog, Petri, Rezugui, and Hippolyte, 2020) established as part of EC 2019-2024 priorities states that everybody in the EU has the right to quality and inclusive education, training and lifelong learning. Its Action Plan target is that 60% of all adults should be participating in training every year by 2030, in 2016 only 37% were. Data on the current EU skill landscape is available via the Skills Panorama, an online tool providing central access to data, information and intelligence on skill needs in occupations, sectors (including construction) and countries (European Commission, 2020). It provides information by policy themes and gives a European perspective on trends for skills supply and demand and skill mismatches, while giving information about national data and sources. Inspection of data from this and other sources reveals that deficiencies still exist. There is a need to adapt existing tools and specify new tools to facilitate the mutual recognition of smart building skills and qualifications in the construction sector, and as such contribute to the increase in the demand for skilled white- and blue-collar workers. Given the dominance of SMEs in the construction sector, it is important to specifically ensure that SME organisations are consulted, and adapted measures implemented to promote their re-skilling to increase their smart building expertise across the project lifecycle. This will be achieved through stakeholder centred definition and harmonisation of a European Qualification Framework (EQF) through the review of roles and skills vs. national training offers.

The EQF is a common European reference framework with the objective to make qualifications clearer across European countries and systems. The implementation of the EQF was based on the Recommendation on the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on 23 April 2008. The EQF was influenced by work conducted in countries such as Australia, Scotland, New Zealand and South Africa (Haut Comité éducation-économie-emploi 2004) who have pioneered the concept of NQF (Bohlinger, 2019). Conversely, the EQF originated from a wide consultation with experts, policymakers and a wide range of studies including work commissioned by the European Commission which provided the fundament for the level descriptors (Coles and Oates, 2004; Winterton, Delamare-Le Deist, and Stringfellow 2006) and the OECD work on 'The Role of National Qualifications Systems in Promoting Lifelong Learning' (Behringer and Coles 2003; Bohlinger 2019).

Covering qualifications at all levels and in all sub-systems of education and training, the EQF provides a comprehensive overview over qualifications in European countries currently involved in its adoption. The core of the EQF is its eight reference levels defined in terms of learning outcomes, i.e., knowledge, skills and autonomy-responsibility. Learning outcomes express what individuals know, understand and are able to do at the end of a learning process. Countries develop national qualifications frameworks (NQFs) to implement the EQF.

It is worth noting that several scholars had questioned if qualifications frameworks in general and the EQF in particular would be able to meet the expectations that had emerged from its development under economic and political pressure (Bohlinger 2019; Allais 2007; Allais et al. 2009; Bohlinger 2007). Moreover, scholars have highlighted the difficulty of assimilating and benchmarking important concepts related to education systems across national borders – a prerequisite for developing qualifications frameworks. Despite concerns raised at a national level, by the end of 2013, 16 EU Member States had completed the EQF process (ICF GHK 2013, 44). In 2017, 39 countries including all 28 EU Member States plus another 11 countries (Albania, Bosnia–Herzegovina, Iceland, Kosovo, Lichtenstein, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland, and Turkey) had adopted the recommendation, and 34 of Them had finished the process in 2018 (Cedefop 2018, 35). When the European Commission celebrated the EQF's 10th anniversary in the same year (in March 2018), it published a communication highlighting the advantages resulting from the EQF. Reflecting the success in implementing the 2008 recommendation, a revised and strengthened Recommendation on the EQF was adopted on 22nd May 2017 by the Education, Youth, Culture and Sport Council (Bohlinger 2019).

In sum, **it is important to develop an EQF adapted to smart buildings. It is also essential to inform the necessary tools and instruments adapted to a wide range of country specific organisational and cultural work practices across Europe.** These tools will include:

- sustainable energy skills passports/registers for workers at regional/national level and support for their take up at EU level;
- mobile applications facilitating the comparison of workers' skills and qualifications between countries;
- new legislative frameworks or public procurement practices;
- initiatives for home and building owners;
- new partnerships with producers and retailers.

3.1.5. Support to the digitalisation of businesses

The built environment is increasingly embracing digital technologies, including control and automation systems, and as such is paving the way to smarter ways of managing our buildings and wider infrastructures. Digitalisation implies major changes in design methods, technologies and tools. Beyond BIM, in the light of technology advancements and societal changes related to buildings in the Industry 5.0 era, there will be a fundamental shift in designing and constructing smart buildings.

Industry 5.0 provides a vision of industry that aims beyond efficiency and productivity as the sole goals and reinforces the role and the contribution of industry to society⁵. It places the wellbeing of the worker at the centre of the production process and uses new technologies to provide prosperity beyond jobs and growth while respecting the production limits of the planet. It complements the existing 'Industry 4.0' approach by specifically putting research and innovation at the service of the transition to a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry. Industry 4.0 refers to the concept of factories in which machines are automated and augmented with cyber-physical systems, the internet of things (IoT), cloud computing, cognitive computing and artificial intelligence, and connected to a system that can visualise the entire production line and control it.

According to ECTP (in the Position Paper of its Digital Built Environment Committee), Construction 5.0 is to be made possible by the 'multiplying' of innovative and proven materials, technologies (the so-called KETs - Key Enabling Technologies), and components, and their integration supported by enhanced data/knowledge management and ICT. It is also made possible by a deep integration of data management and ICT platforms and tools in all phases of the construction process, placing the wellbeing of the worker at the centre of this process. The ECTP advocates that the value-chain should drastically evolve from a linear operational and economic model into a **transformed, fully integrated, human-centric construction value chain**.

With up to 98% of its construction chain composed of SMEs and micro-enterprises characterised by decreasing innovation activity, low rates of technological adoption and decreasing efficiency, **digitalisation of SMEs in the construction sector is therefore strategic for the EU**, according to the European Commission in a 2019 report on the digitalisation of the construction sector and SMEs. **However, construction sector workers are typically not knowledgeable or lack access to digital tools that could facilitate their work.** The 3 priority actions suggested by the report include the provision of lifelong (digital) skills development for (blue-collars) employees within the construction sector through trainings.

It is essential for organisations to develop the right capabilities to leverage their knowledge if they are to compete successfully in the smart buildings market. Organisations are essentially "social arrangements for achieving controlled performance in pursuit of collective goals" (Huczynski and Buchanan, 2001). Whatever the goals of the organisation (project management, production of building materials, creation of building

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/industry-50_en

designs, construction of buildings), the arrangements necessary for achieving controlled performance will involve the management of certain constant elements (Rezgui et al., 2005), including: people (staff), technology (systems), tasks (skills) and structure (Leavitt, 1965).

The knowledge organisation can be defined through its ability to adapt to the changing environment by creating new knowledge, disseminating it effectively and embodying this knowledge into practice (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). A knowledge-creating company is well placed to provide continuous innovation (Nonaka et al., 2000). Innovation increases when it takes an inter-organisational dimension and knowledge is shared and created across organisations and the supply chain (Ding and Peters, 2000; Levy et al., 2001).

Companies with knowledge management programmes need efficient and effective management of their codified knowledge and best practice (usually maintained within corporate knowledge bases) to ensure creation of new knowledge, its distribution across organisational extent and ready accessibility to all members. In the construction sector, innovation is perceived as “the act of introducing and using new ideas, technologies, products and/or processes aimed at solving problems, viewing things differently, improving efficiency and effectiveness, or enhancing standards of living” (CERF, 2000). Project-based organisation focuses on the production and/or delivery side of a firm’s business (Artto, 1998), and is characterised by the coexistence of a continuing organisation structure, typically based on functional departments with a temporary organisational structure based on project teams (Barrett and Sexton, 2006; Grant, 1997; Rezgui, 2007).

To continue to push the construction industry forward, it is critical that a new perspective is adopted in the digital transformation agenda, including embodying a whole life-cycle system of systems approach, underpinned by modern information modelling standards and improved governance and business processes. By rising to meet this challenge, BIM can continue to contribute towards, and benefit from, progress towards a digital and circular economy, which will allow it to transition from simply delivering smart construction to truly enabling smart built environments.

3.2. Lessons learnt from Horizon 2020 projects

3.2.1. Overview

A few H2020 projects have addressed the topic of digital education & upskilling: some of them are pictured in Figure 7. Although it is likely that this list is not exhaustive, it covers the projects represented (or mentioned) in the task force – more details are provided in Annex 1.

Figure 7: Relevant H2020 projects identified by the task force members

Key lessons learnt or conclusions from some of these projects have already been presented in the state of the art. We will now dive deeper in the lessons learnt from a few selected projects.

3.2.2. Lessons learnt from the INSTRUCT project

INSTRUCT intends to create a complete operational framework to increase the number of skilled building professionals and blue-collar workers over the whole value chain (both for renovations and new constructions), and offer a set of service to support raising awareness of home and building owners and tenants about the benefits of sustainable energy skills, and the public authorities for the development of new legislative frameworks, e.g. requirements for skilled workers in public procurement.

Lessons learned so far include:

- Training needs to adapt to an evolving and dynamic landscape characterised by continuous technology evolution and the need for adapted and tailored training for the construction workforce.
- Training is not static, it is dynamic.
- We are moving towards an adapted, tailored approach.
- The platform (<http://www.energy-education.com/>) could be used as a vehicle for knowledge, experience, and best practice sharing within organisations, across projects and beyond, in the construction industry.

3.2.3. Lessons learnt from the BIMplement project

The aim of the project was to improve building energy efficiency thanks to the use of BIM process and of BIM models on the construction sites. Several approaches and focus have been given to this issue in the different partners countries: Netherlands, Spain, Poland, Lithuania and France.

The focus has been given to SMEs and their employees, and to craftsmen, that represent a large part of the building construction sector. What has been observed on real projects in France is that when a project is designed with BIM, whatever its level of detail and quality, site workers, including site managers, never get to see and be presented the 3D BIM model(s). They only receive a (large) amount of 2D plans, created from the BIM model. This means that site managers and foremen have to figure out the complexity of a nZEB building and the interfaces between batches only from multiple 2D plans. In practice, building companies and craftsmen mainly consider the plans and documents they are involved with, and only the site manager tries to get a global view of the project. In addition, these plans are not always updated, in particular when they are paper plans.

Lessons learned include:

- Presently, BIM models are designed by project managers' teams or by large companies' design offices only for their own design and calculation needs, and to answer regulation requirements, and if drafted, client's requirements. They are not designed to be used by blue-collar workers on a construction site. Site workers only get 2D plans and project managers consider that the designed BIM model will be (almost) identical to the realised construction.
- Clients and owners, whether public or private, mainly ignore the BIM stakes, have no specific BIM specifications and have no precise BIM requests. They let the project manager implement their BIM process on their own.
- SME companies and craftsmen almost never need to design BIM models. They have a very low BIM maturity, do not know/understand the interest of using BIM models during the implementation phase. BIM communication only presents BIM as a complex design tool, that needs high-skilled human resources and costly software. SME and craftsmen never feel concerned with this topic, and then, consider they have nothing to do with BIM.

BIMplement demonstrated that, even in different European economical contexts, one- or two-days training sessions, realised on the construction site, and based on the use of freeware viewers and of the project's BIM model, appears sufficient to understand the interest of using BIM models during project implementation and apprehend all basics viewers tools.

Onsite training is better accepted by companies, because there is less transportation waste of time, training is more concrete and directly applicable to the project construction.

Good practices and recommendations:

In order to deal with a BIM project in its global aspect, site workers (mainly site managers, foremen and craftsmen) need to be trained to handle freeware viewers and their associated tools.

1. Open and handle BIM models:
 - a. 'read' a BIM model, that is wander around in the models, add or mask each of them or elements of the models, and so directly visualise the project in 3D, instead of figuring it out from lot of plans;
 - b. virtually check interfaces between trades, and visualise potential conflicts with other batches;
 - c. get to use the updated plans and models available by the project manager, for instance on collaborative platforms.
2. Take advantage of BIM object data
 - a. take note of the BIM object data, given by the project manager;
 - b. enrich the model with documents dedicated to implementation, such as
 - pictures of work realised, before finishing coating,
 - implementation guides and technical documentation,

- information about the effective site implemented product.

3. Use cross-trade and cross-level communication tools

- ask any project stakeholder for precisions, based on an image extracted and linked to the BIM model;
- participate in the elaboration of REAL as-built model, while transmitting to the person(s) in charge of the updating of the project model (project manager or building company), any change in the project.

The BIM process and the BIM model have to be enlarged from design only to site implementation. It means that BIM process has to include building companies who do not design any BIM model, and give them access to BIM models enriched with documents, technical details, ... that are often difficult to find on time on the construction site.

- during site meetings, project managers and site managers should use the BIM model to enhance cross-trade and cross-level collaboration, explain the difficult implementation points, and use the BIM model as a database accessible to all site-workers where to find all guides, quality control sheets, detailed drawing ... and 2D plans.
- The BIM models have to have a good quality and all conflicts solved so that its export into ifc format makes it accessible with any viewers. This is essential for site workers to have confidence and interest in BIM, and convince them to use the BIM models and attached documents for a better implementation of nZEB buildings

Clients and general contractors are key partners. During BIMplement, several clients and general contractors decided to inscribe their demands regarding BIM use and BIM process into their project specifications, namely ask for an enlargement of the BIM process to include building companies and site workers and impose training clauses in their contracts.

When clients are convinced of the interest of using BIM models on construction sites in order to improve site implementation, training clauses and adapted BIM specifications can make the change. This process be launched through specific training sessions dedicated to them.

Training sessions must be adapted to each stakeholder, in terms of schedule, contents, issues and examples, benefits, language and vocabulary, duration ... In particular, design teams have to understand that the whole value chain should be involved in the BIM process, including clients and building companies, SME and craftsmen. As for building companies, the pedagogical approach becomes as important as the content in order to overcome the building companies site workers reluctance about new practices.

3.2.4. Lessons learnt from the BUSLeague project

BUSLeague aims to address and overcome the challenges of the stimulation of demand for energy skilled workforce (demand side), along with hands-on capacity building to increase the number of skilled workforce across the building design, operation and maintenance value chain (supply side). BUSLeague is working on upscaling successful training methods and techniques which have already been developed in previous EU and National initiatives such as BUILD UP Skills, Construction. BUSLeague is strengthened by experienced anthropology researchers and educational technology researchers in order to prove impact and to optimise the blends for stimulating demand and optimising learning transfer of applied learning means and materials.

Results

As part of BUSLeague, an approach to motivate job seekers to join the construction industry, including women, has been developed and demonstrated in Hauts-de-France. It consists in organising a demonstration in a public space (for instance in small towns), using the mobile centre from Practee (see Figure 6) as well as

a virtual reality helmet, to enable local job seekers to better understand the variety of opportunities offered by the construction sector, and – when there is an interest – to directly identify their training needs.

Lessons learned include:

- To ensure high quality trainings, evaluation of available trainings, collaboration between training providers and the dissemination of cross-sector knowledge are essential.
- Establishing training and consultation centres for building professionals and end users is the basis for stimulating the market demand for nZEBs.
- The development of qualification registers and SkillPassportsystems endorsed by relevant branch organisations and national authorities are necessary.
- Training should be integrated to the construction site whenever possible: it has to be hands-on and included to daily work, to address reluctance related to training (i.e. avoids ‘locking’ a worker for several days in a classroom, no waste of time, benefit of acquiring new knowledge is directly visible).
- Trainers should themselves be regularly trained or benefit from a mentorship, in particular if they deliver on-site training
- The trainings should be driven by the clients’ demand: training can be made compulsory as part of tendering processes (however this only works for big projects with more than a dozen of persons).
- It is necessary to educate company managers and owners (most of them were trained more than 20 years ago...) on the importance of new tools and of acquiring skills to use these tools. They should also be trained to monitor novelties and disruptive innovations in the field of smart building.

3.3. Other initiatives related to education and upskilling

Name of initiative	Relevant inputs
<p>Construction Cluster Ireland</p> <p>https://cc-ireland.ie/</p>	<p>The CCI acts as a catalyst to accelerate the competitiveness and internationalisation of Irish SMEs through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Addressing Skill Shortages ▪ Increasing Productivity and Efficiency ▪ Digitally Transforming ▪ Embracing Sustainability & Circularity ▪ Implementing Modern Methods of Construction <p>The CCI aims to increase competitiveness of the cluster firms, collectively address opportunities and roadblocks, improve access to knowledge, talent, market, research and innovation, assist in securing finance via the participation of publicly funded agencies and finally, build alignment around common agendas. The CCI addresses the following activities: Collaborative Innovation Projects, access to funds and supports, research partnership and training opportunities.</p>

4. Barriers and drivers

4.1. Barriers

Barriers to the market uptake of smart buildings (and the strengthening of the related ecosystem) related to education & upskilling were reviewed and prioritised by the task force. The top barriers are highlighted below.

BARRIERS	
VALUE CHAIN	Fragmented and competitive sector, with a lot of SMEs, leading to complex communication, coordination and cooperation among trades
	Insufficient up-to-date knowledge of smart technologies (and 'soft skills' to sell them) and lack of companies able to provide training about latest products
	Lack of construction workers, ageing workforce
SOCIAL	Smart buildings still perceived as a niche market, hence limited resources and long-term investment by contractors, starting with training (time, money)
	Resistance to change, lack of awareness of the value of energy skills, lack of motivation to get trained on smart buildings topics
TECHNICAL	Vendor lock-in with proprietary software, lack of interoperability and lack of open standards/communication protocols
	Outdated curricula, not able to keep up with the rate of innovation, lack of competent trainers, limited training infrastructure
	Complex training landscape
ECONOMIC	Cost of upskilling trainings and uncertainty on available incentives and funding
	Lack of financial resources for training centers to update programmes and their teaching material
REGULATION	Lack of a regulatory enforced smart building standard, which complicates the market and hinders the development of effective and up-to-date vocational education programmes

Top barriers according to the Task Force

Figure 8: Overview of main barriers

4.2. Drivers

The drivers identified by the task force are as illustrated below. As for the barriers, the strongest drivers (according to the task force members) are related to users.

Figure 9: Overview of main drivers

5. Gaps

Various activities required to overcome the barriers and leverage the drivers (related to education and upskilling) were suggested and prioritised by the task force members (Table 1). The priority ones according to the task force are in bold.

Table 1: Suggested R&I and go-to-market activities

Type of activity	Activities
R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perform an in-depth analysis, involving all stakeholders, of the skills and competencies required in relation to smart buildings (what’s new, what can be transferred from more traditional trades), and review the regional variations in skills availability and training capacities - Develop new initial and continuous training programmes related to smart buildings: frequently updated, on-site where possible (with more hands-on and practical experience), with clear learning outcomes, optimised geographically to be close to the SMEs, clearly referenced (i.e. accessible and up-to-date catalogue), supported by innovative types of incentives for SMEs - Develop a one-stop-shop online portal enabling workers of all ages to make informed career choices, matching unemployed people with the demand from the construction sector, and providing upskilling guidance according to the latest needs

Demonstration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrate BIM in practice with real cases, to attract new, younger workers, and convince existing workers (and clients) of the need to acquire skills to use it - Demonstrate on-site training for on-site workers, using innovative approaches such as mobile training centres
Scaling up & industrialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reinforce the cooperation between educational institutions and the industry to improve the quality of training - Foster cross-training and peer-learning on-site between similar companies (or within companies) through ad hoc incentives and develop cluster actions - Use ambassadors/'influencers' (e.g., local associations, clusters, construction material/DIY retailers) to increase outreach to SME owners and convince them to invest in training and get trained themselves - Better inform persons in charge of vocational guidance in VET and HEI with regards to new curricula related to smart buildings / digitalised construction sector - 'Train the trainer': Environmental/governmental agencies to provide necessary support to make sure trainers are comfortable with the latest technologies and update their courses. Implement mentorship of trainers where possible, to share good practices
Certification & standardisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and implement new professional qualifications related to smart buildings and energy efficiency, together with procedures to check that these qualifications are up to date to encourage continuous learning, and to support the standardisation of energy efficiency practices in the construction sector
Regulation & legal framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate regulation and policy making to training courses and curricula - Make training compulsory (for instance through a 'training clause' in private and public procurement), and monitor implementation through government bodies

6. Conclusion

This document formalises the collaborative work performed by the members of SmartBuilt4EU task force 4, on a voluntary basis, during the period May 2022-August 2022. It also integrates the feedback collected during 1) a peer review conducted by VITO in October 2022, and 2) an open consultation process in October 2022.

Based on an analysis of the state of the art and the identification of barriers and drivers, the main objective of this paper is to detect some research and innovation gaps that still need to be addressed in the coming years in order to improve education and upskilling related to smart building solutions and systems.

This white paper will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda that the SmartBuilt4EU consortium will present to the European Commission.

To receive the updates on the SmartBuil4EU task forces, white papers and events, please register here:
<https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/join-our-community/>

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8. Annex 1: list of H2020 projects reviewed

Table 2: list of relevant EU projects

Project	Status	Contact in TF	Weblink	Relevant inputs
	Ongoing	Avril Behan	https://www.ariseproject.eu	<p>ARISE is a European funded project that aims to support the upskilling of the design and construction professionals on the topics of energy efficient buildings and Building Information Modelling (BIM) processes.</p> <p>ARISE will apply digitalization both as a learning method and as a framework of job-based construction skills of the future, multiplying the effects of the green transition skills. The novel training method will make the learning process attractive and effective, facilitating its accessibility through a smartphone and a user-friendly web-based platform.</p>
	Closed	Anna Moreno	https://platform.energybimcert.eu/	<p>The BIMcert project will develop a blended, fully supported suite of Building Information Modelling training curriculum and tools, which will allow geographically dispersed construction project teams to use technology to enhance information exchange and collaboration.</p> <p>The program content will be developed in a 'accessible open' format that will allow middle managers, blue-collar workers and other 'work tied' industry personnel to access the training and accreditation in order to increase their BIM skills, utilise these in their work increasing energy efficient construction and improve their skills/employment mobility.</p>
	Closed	Myriam Olivier	https://www.bimplement-project.eu/	<p>BIMplement covered several European countries, with tailored approaches adapted to the local market context.</p> <p>In Spain, focus was also given to SME and craftsmen. A "catalogue of constructive elements", web application, has been created from which the construction solutions in IFC format can be downloaded.</p> <p>In Netherlands, a "just in-time" data process for on-site implementation has been developed. It is a step-by-step guide related to a real project data with which every subcontractor/supplier can identify their starting situation and assess their work better.</p> <p>In Poland and Lithuania, focus has been given to large companies, and employees have been trained to use BIM models on construction site, linked to specific software such as quantity take-off.</p>
	Closed	Irini Barbero	www.bimeet.eu/	<p>BIMET project leverages the take-up of ICT and BIM through a significant upgrade of the skills and capacities of the EU construction workforce. This project is built around a strong consortium relying on educational and research & technology expertise, robust experience of accrediting bodies, training supply chain and a wide engagement of industry led best practice.</p>

<p>BUILD UP SKILLS ENERGY TRAINING FOR BUILDERS</p>	Closed	/	https://buildupskills.eu/	<p>BUILD UP Skills was a strategic initiative under the Intelligent Energy Europe (IEE) programme (Calls for proposals 2011-2013) to boost continuing or further education and training of craftsmen and other on-site construction workers and systems installers in the building sector.</p> <p>The final aim was to increase the number of qualified workers across Europe to deliver renovations offering a high energy performance as well as new, nearly zero-energy buildings. The initiative addressed skills in relation to energy efficiency and renewables in all types of buildings.</p>
<p>BUS LEAGUE</p>	Ongoing	Henri Le Marois	https://busleague.eu/	<p>The overall aim of BUSLeague is to address and overcome the challenges of the stimulation of demand for energy skilled workforce (demand side), along with hands-on capacity building to increase the number of skilled workforce across the building design, operation and maintenance value chain (supply side).</p> <p>BUSLeague will achieve this objective by developing and implementing a cross European recognition of energy skills, together with upscaling successful training methods and techniques which have already been developed in previous EU and National initiatives such as BUILD UP Skills, Construction Skills.</p>
<p>BUS GoCircular</p>	Ongoing	/	https://busgocircular.eu/	<p>BUS-GoCircular understands the importance of a green energy workforce within the construction sector. The aim of the project is to address and overcome the challenges faced when implementing real change through equipping a green energy skilled workforce.</p>
<p>INSTRUCT</p>	Ongoing	Iriani Barbero	https://instructproject.eu/	<p>INSTRUCT intends to create a complete operational framework to increase the number of skilled building professionals and blue-collar workers over the whole value chain (both for renovations and new constructions), and offer a set of service to support raising awareness of home and building owners and tenants about the benefits of sustainable energy skills, and the public authorities for the development of new legislative frameworks, e.g. requirements for skilled workers in public procurement.</p>
<p>NET UBIEP</p>	Closed	Avril Behan	http://www.net-ubiep.eu/	<p>Net-UBIEP aims at increasing energy performance of buildings by wide spreading and strengthening the use of BIM, during the life cycle of the building.</p> <p>BIM Qualification Models to tackle the problem of energy competences gap in the existing buildings sector as a whole. Each BIM Qualification Model will be composed by a BIM Training Scheme and a BIM Qualification and Certification Scheme.</p> <p>Net-UBIEP Project will increase energy performance related competences of 6 professional figures: BIM evaluator, BIM facility manager, BIM manager, BIM coordinator, BIM expert, BIM user.</p>
<p>PROF / TRAC Open Training and Qualification Platform on nZEB construction and renovation</p>	Closed	/	http://proftrac.eu/open-training-platform-for-nzeb-professionals.html	<p>PROF/TRAC made up a comprehensive list of technologies and interdisciplinary skills related to nZEBs. These technologies and skills represent the “highest common denominator” for the qualification of the targeted building professionals, meaning that any construction sector white-collar involved in nZEB</p>

				design and construction will necessarily have at least one of these skills. The more skilled the professionals, the more successful the nZEB design.
 PRO-Heritage	Closed	/	https://www.pro-heritage.eu/	The EU-funded PRO-Heritage project will establish a permanent education resource for professionals and craftsmen providing excellent competences and skills for built heritage and support the exchange of those competences and skills across Europe.
 SEetheSkills <small>VISIBLE VALIDATED VALUABLE</small>	Ongoing	/	https://seetheskills.eu/	SEetheSkills is H2020 project (2021-2024) that stands in front of the challenge for energy efficient construction of new and renovation of existing building stocks. It will act at market level in order to stimulate the demand for new or upgraded skills in renewables and energy efficiency. The project will promote the visibility of sustainable energy skills in the construction of new and renovation of existing buildings stocks by creating an online repository. It will also enable the validation of energy skills to raise their value.
 TRAIN4SUSTAIN	Ongoing	/	https://train4sustain.eu/	TRAIN4SUSTAIN (T4S) will stimulate demand for skilled construction sector professionals (architects, contractors-SMEs and workers) through raising acceptance of regional and national qualifications and skills on the EU construction market. T4S project will foster a common understanding of sustainable energy skills across Europe by promoting a competence quality standard, a European Skills Registry and a Skills Passport for facilitating transnational recognition of learning outcomes and skill levels of existing qualifications and vocational trainings.